

Cryptic-Steganography: A Data Hiding Approach

Dr. Shilpa Pund-Dange, Assistant Professor, Modern College, Pune-5.

Dr. Nivedita Mahajan, Assistant Professor, Modern College, Pune-5.

Abstract: Data hiding is a broader notion found in Data Security. Cryptography and Steganography are two main disciplines applied for data security. This paper discusses double-layer security using Cryptography and Steganography. A sender encrypts a secret message using the RSA algorithm with Mersenne Primes. The encrypted message (ciphertext) is then hidden into an innocent image to get a stego image using the Steganography algorithm with Catalan-Lucas sequence. Three stego keys are generated while embedding a message. At the receiver side, the ciphertext is extracted from the stego image by applying stego keys using an extraction module of a given steganography algorithm. An extracted ciphertext is then decrypted using a private key with RSA algorithm using Mersenne Primes. From the above experiment, it is clear that the subsistence of hidden messages is not noticeable by the visual attack.

Keywords: Cryptic-Steganography, Mersenne Primes, Catalan series, Lucas series, Data hiding, Bit plane slicing.

1. Introduction

In the current era, due to the fast growth in the network and data communication technologies, valuable data transfers via the Internet grows rapidly. This data suffers many security breaches if it is transferred without protection. To avoid these security breaches, many cryptography techniques are used. Cryptography means scrambling a message in such a way that it can't be recognize by an unauthorized person. Cryptography techniques are broadly categorized as Private key Cryptography and Public Key Cryptography. In private key cryptography, a single key is used for encryption as well as decryption. The private key must remain confidential to its owner. Key transportation and distribution are the main issues of private Key cryptography. To avoid this issue, public key cryptography is chosen for this research. On the other hand, another important feature of Public Key cryptography is its capability to create a Digital Signature. RSA is one of the famous public key cryptographic algorithms. The security of RSA lies in the size of the key. The longer the key size more is the security. In this paper, we are using a variation in RSA as RSA using Mersenne primes. The security of RSA is based on the hard problem of integer factorization. The use of Mersenne primes rather than simple primes generates a long digit key which enhances the security of RSA algorithms. For multi-layer security, RSA algorithms with Mersenne Prime[1] is coupled with steganography using the bit plane slicing technique. A modified steganography algorithm using Catalan-Lucas Series [2] is used for embedding data into an image.

2. Cryptic-Steganography Model

A pictorial representation of the model is depicted in the following fig.

Fig. 1. Cryptic-Steganography Model

The execution steps of the model are as follows:

At the Sender:

1. Read the values of modulus ' c ' and the public exponent ' e ' from the receiver.
2. Read a secret data called plaintext.
3. Apply the encryption module of '*RSA algorithm using Mersenne Primes*' [1].
4. Character-by-character plaintext is converted into cipher text by using modulus ' c ' and the public exponent ' e '.
5. Apply embedding module of the '*Modified Steganographic algorithm using Catalan-Lucas series*[2]' to hide the cipher text into an innocent image to get the stego image. Bit plane slicing technique is used in this algorithm which is explained in section 3.
6. Three keys are generated while embedding.
7. Pass the stego image over an insecure channel.
8. Pass the stego keys to the receiver over a secure channel.

At the receiver:

1. Accept the stego image.
2. Accept the stego keys.
3. Apply *extraction* module of the '*Modified Steganographic algorithm using Catalan-Lucas series* to extract ciphertext from the stego image with the help of Stego keys.
4. The receiver knows the private key.
5. Apply the decryption module of '*RSA algorithm using Mersenne Primes*' on the cipher text to get the plaintext back with the help of the Private key.

The following figures explain the different states of the model:

a. Plaintext file (164 bytes)

b. Ciphertext file(7.90 KB)

c. Cover Image(768 KB)

d. Stego Image(768 KB, PSNR 39.66)

e. Cipher text (Extracted)

f. Plaintext decrypted (164 bytes)

Fig. 2. Different States of Cryptic-Steganography Model

3. Bit-Plane Slicing

Bit plane slicing technique is used in the steganography algorithm. Steganography using 8-bit plane slicing is proposed by Chakraborty S., Jalal A.S., and Bhatnagar[4]. This paper introduced an irreversible technique to hide a secret image into the cover image. The secret image is called a payload. An RGB color image is taken as a cover image and a greyscale image is taken as a payload. The dimensions of the payload image must be less than or equal to the cover image. X-OR operation is used for data embedding.

Fig. 3. 16 bit plane slices

To increase data security and hiding capacity the above algorithm is modified. Instead of representing a pixel intensity value by 8-bit, it is represented by higher number of bits. The binary sequence is used for 8-bit representation. For 8-bit representation, 8 bit planes are generated. If we embed data in LSB bit planes, the distortion is not noticeable in the image but the hiding capacity is less. To increase the hiding capacity, if data is embedded in higher bit planes in this model, it distorts the image which is recognizable to the human eye. To avoid this issue, Famous Number Sequences introduced a new representation of a pixel. A pixel intensity value is represented by more number of bits. By using the Fibonacci series and Lucas series a pixel intensity value between (0..255) is represented by 12 bits and ultimately 12 virtual bit planes are generated[5]. The Catalan number sequence is not enough to represent every integer in between (0..255). Hence by considering the union of Catalan and Fibonacci sequence, each pixel intensity value is represented by 15 bits and 15 virtual bit planes are generated at last. By considering the union of the Catalan and Lucas sequence, each pixel intensity value is represented by 16 bits and ultimately 16 virtual bit planes are generated[6]. This increases the hiding capacity of the image and also increases security. The pictorial representation of 16 bit plane is shown in Fig. 3.

R, G, and B components of an image are decomposed into 16 bit planes. Data embedded among a few middle bit planes are given in the flow diagram Fig. 4. The stego image so generated is visually the same as that of the original image. But some changes are observed in the size of the image after converting it into 16 bit by applying the Catalan Lucas series algorithm using Zeckendorf's Theorem [3]. Jpeg, png, and tiff images change their size after converting into 16 bit by applying this algorithm. Only .bmp images have the same size before and after embedding. Hence, .bmp images with variant intensity are best suitable for this algorithm.

4. Observations:

1. For RSA, the size of the file successfully encrypted and decrypted depends on the key size and ultimately the values of the prime numbers p and q . If a fast processor with a high memory configuration is available then it can work fine for file size up to 5KB.
2. The security of RSA depends on two mathematical facts. The first one is the factorization of number c . In the proposed system because of the use of Mersenne Primes c becomes very large which is known as a mathematical attack. The second is trying all possible private keys called a brute force attack [7]. As the generated private key is a very large digit number it will take years of computational efforts to crack it.
3. For the Steganography module, the size of the file successfully encrypted and decrypted depends on the cover image dimensions ($row * column$). The length of the message in a file to be encrypted must be less than the image size ($row * column$). Depending on the image size the computation efforts increases.
4. When cryptography and steganography modules combine, the file size to be hidden is reduced (i.e. bytes only). The reason is that the RSA algorithm proposed here, each character of the secret message is replaced by a very large number depending on the size of the public key c .
E.g. Plaintext file of size 164 bytes passed for encryption using RSA algorithms with Mersenne Prime[1], the encrypted file becomes very large i.e. 7.90 KB. This encrypted file works as an input to the steganography module.

$$7.90 \text{ KB} = 63200 \text{ bits}$$

The hiding capacity of an image is 16 bits/pixel.

No. of pixels required to hide the encrypted file is= $63200 \div 16 = 3950$

As an encrypted file is 7.90 KB it needs cover image of 3950 pixels for embedding.

5. PSNR is often expressed on a logarithmic scale in dB (decibel) [8]. PSNR value below 30dB shows degradable quality of the image. PSNR value greater than or equal to 30dB of the image is difficult to recognize by the human eyes. Fig. 2 (D) shows the PSNR value 39.66 which maintained the quality of an image.

5. Conclusion

This paper proposed a Cryptic-Steganography technique using the RSA algorithm with Mersenne Primes in combination with 'Modified Steganographic algorithm using Catalan-Lucas series'. Because of the use of Mersenne primes, it generates a long digit key which is difficult to be factorize. By applying 'Modified Steganographic algorithm using Catalan-Lucas series' generated ciphertext is embedded in an image. Using the bit-plane slicing technique, an image is decomposed into 16 bit planes as mentioned in section 3. Data is embedded into the R, G, and B planes of the image. The ciphertext gets extracted from the stego image using the three stego keys. 16-bit representation of data, as well as the cover image, provide high security

for embedded data. Hence the above-discussed Cryptic-Steganography model provides double-layer security using Cryptography and Steganography.

Fig. 4. Flow Diagram for 8 Bit Plane Slicing using X-OR

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